

PHILOSOPHICAL SCIENCES

FORMATION OF IDEALS AND NORMS OF CONSTRUCTION AND ORGANIZATION OF HISTORICAL KNOWLEDGE AT HERODOTUS'S HISTORY

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Abstract

The article examines the main approaches to the formation of Herodotus' initial ideals and norms of historical scientific knowledge. The main attention is paid to the ideals and norms of description and explanation, as well as the ideals and norms of evidence and validity of historical knowledge. The ideological and methodological foundations on which Herodotus builds his own system of ideals and norms of science are revealed.

Keywords: historical science, Ancient Greece, Herodotus, worldview foundations, methodology of historical cognition, ideals and norms of historical knowledge, ideals and norms of description and explanation, ideals and norms of evidence and validity.

The very nature of historical science generally defines the ideals and norms for constructing and organizing knowledge—the presentation must correspond to the chronological succession of events. However, Herodotus's work is structured somewhat differently than might be expected, given his status as the "father of history." The narrative, in general, is constructed chronologically, but not rigidly and unambiguously. Rather, chronology is present as a tendency. The primary guideline is the creation of a coherent historical canvas.

Herodotus's previously described picture of the reality under readily study accommodates this. It represents a holistic historical process, with a unified historical space and time, filled with interconnected events subject to a single law.

Since these are the ideals and norms of historical research, time is the primary connecting element here. Herodotus's general understanding of time has also been discussed previously. Therefore, in this case, it is necessary to demonstrate how it is implemented in relation to the construction of the "History."

We once emphasize again: time in Herodotus is epic; "He lives in a world of centuries and decades. It's difficult to find meticulously precise, let alone well-reasoned, dating in his work" [10, pp. 151-152]. This understanding of time necessarily follows from the overall goal of his work: Herodotus sought to penetrate as far into the past as possible, to connect recent events with those described in mythology. And there, precise dating was simply impossible. As a result, the "father of history" handles time quite freely when determining the sequence of events described in his work.

This does not mean, however, that Herodotus pays no attention to chronology at all. On the contrary, he used and compared various chronologies available to him (the Olympiads, the reigns of kings, the years of archons, the time of the succession of generations) [13, p. 151]. But, we repeat, his primary focus was on identifying and describing the succession of events as an interconnected process. And the continuity of events was

more important to him than possible overlaps in chronology. Successive, interconnected, and interdependent events unite and unify space, making it an element of a single history. [14, p. 30].

Furthermore, the concept of a unified time is formed on this same basis. "For Herodotus, the idea of the continuity of events and empires stands above (my emphasis – S.M.) individual chronologies and universalizes various chronological systems" [13, p. 151]. As a result, on the basis of a unified historical space and a universal concept of time, Herodotus lays the foundations for ideas about universal history [ibid., p. 152]. Within its boundaries, shifts in specific chronological dates prove permissible, as noted earlier. It is precisely these foundations that determine the organization and construction of knowledge within the framework of "History."

These norms of organizing and constructing knowledge were already noted as essential features of the "History" by ancient authors. Thus, the previously mentioned Dionysius of Halicarnassus, comparing Herodotus and Thucydides, wrote: "The next task of the historian is to distribute the material and put everything in its place. How, then, does each of them distribute and arrange what is reported? Thucydides follows chronology, and Herodotus strives to grasp a series of interconnected events. As a result, Thucydides creates ambiguity and makes it difficult to follow the course of events... Herodotus nowhere breaks up the narrative. Thus, it turns out that Thucydides, having chosen only one event as his theme, dismembered the whole into many parts, while Herodotus, having touched on many different topics, created a harmonious whole (emphasis mine – S.M.)" [Quoted from 10, p. 385].

All of the above elements — the philosophical foundations, worldview, ideals, and norms of scientific research:

1. *Define (explicitly or implicitly) the content of the basic concepts that structure the content of a specific scientific discipline, in this case, the concept of "historical fact."*

In Herodotus, this term has no clear meaning. In epistemological terms, it is also a form of knowledge, intermediate between the sensory and rational levels of cognition, a concept-image. Therefore, the content of "historical facts," that is, the information included in "History," is internally contradictory. Herodotus makes no fundamental distinction between mythological stories and the events he witnessed.

2. *They establish procedures for transforming existing source material into a "historical description, a historical fact," which is already an element of the empirical basis of science.*

Herodotus sets the task of recording the obtained information, comprehending it, and comparing it with one another. When in doubt, in the absence of sufficient grounds for preference, different points of view are retained. Next, they generalize the existing information, identify commonalities and patterns, and apply them to understanding new data. This approach, as has been demonstrated, has allowed historical scholarship to preserve a wealth of valuable information that the author of "History" himself did not consider reliable.

3. *Describe the methods and approaches of a historian working with scientific facts.* Herodotus interprets facts and generalizes them. On this basis, he establishes a general pattern in historical events and constructs his own concept of the historical process. New information is transformed into scientific facts in his work based on this existing concept, integrated into it, even though it may be based on chronologically and historically unreliable information.

Let us also consider Herodotus's implementation of the above-mentioned methodological principles in addressing specific problems in his "History."

Research Object. The object of study is vast. Herodotus sets the task of describing all known history in all known territories, from mythological narratives to contemporary events. The lives of peoples are described in considerable detail, but socioeconomic and cultural history are absent.

Causality in History. According to Herodotus, causality in history is determined by two factors. First, the course of unified history is determined by the presence of a supra-cosmic law—an incontestable fate, or destiny, which punishes anyone who seizes (or seeks to seize) more happiness than is destined for them. This fundamental law of history, realized in a single historical process, explains everything that happens. Second, history is characterized by specific individuals and personified states, represented by their rulers, pursuing their own motives and goals.

The Value of Historical Knowledge. Herodotus believed that all information that could be collected about human history, both reliable and unreliable, was valuable. It must be preserved in memory.

Sources of Knowledge. Herodotus collected all information from the most diverse sources available to him: documents, written eyewitness accounts, memoirs, myths, narratives, etc.

What should be included in the text of a scholarly work. According to Herodotus, everything "that seems worthy of attention." This last clarification practically meant that the "father of history" included information

only after serious consideration, and not all the material he possessed. As a result, the original principle of "preserving everything" underwent a significant transformation.

Form of knowledge recording. Before Herodotus, "logos" was a prose narrative with genealogical content and elements of mythological criticism. Herodotus retained this term for his work, but its content changed fundamentally. "Logos" became a systematic presentation of material based on uniform methodological principles.

The problem of the truth of knowledge and the attitude toward other points of view. Herodotus clearly acknowledges the existence of different points of view. In his "History," he presents several versions of events simultaneously. He may either state the one he considers preferable, or consider them equal if he has no additional arguments.

Herodotus is the true "father of history"—in terms of the breadth of his subject matter and research, the content and depth of his methodological approaches, and the diversity of his sources. In this sense, F. Engels's assessment of ancient philosophy as a whole is entirely applicable to his place and role in the formation and development of historical science: "In the diverse forms of Greek philosophy, almost all later types of worldviews are already present in embryo, in the process of their emergence" [12, p. 369]. Subsequently, over the course of a millennium, historical science began to develop within the framework defined by Thucydides.

The 20th century saw an expansion of the research field and sources of historical science: from purely event-based history to the notorious "structures of everyday life," from documents to oral testimony, from global events to microhistory. As a result, according to the aphoristic judgment of A. Momigliano (1908-1987, Italian-British historian of antiquity and historiographer), Herodotus truly became the "Father of History" in the 20th century [10, p. 394].

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